

IMPLEMENTED REFORMS ON THE INTEGRATION OF THE EDUCATION SECTOR.

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Abstract: Today, large-scale works are being carried out in our country to create a higher education system that meets the main directions of socio-economic development and the requirements of international standards. In particular, the fact that great attention is being paid to education and science makes the scientific community endlessly happy. This article provides information about the reforms implemented in the field of education.

Key words: integration, scientific potential, pedagogy, competence, innovation.

The socio-economic changes taking place in our republic, the reforms that are being rapidly implemented in all areas, the search for new models of self-development competence formation in students studying in higher education institutions, the organization of the educational process based on the requirements of the times, implementation of innovative programs in the field of production into the educational process, modernization of the material and technical base of higher education institutions, wide spread of mutually beneficial social cooperation with scientific research institutes, international projects, colleges, schools, preschool educational organizations, etc. is advancing the issues of establishment.

On June 16 of this year, under the chairmanship of the head of state Sh. Mirziyoyev, at the meeting of the video selector dedicated to the priority tasks in the higher education system, the head of the state indicated 4 priority tasks in the field:

The first is to increase the role of management boards of higher education institutions and expand the powers of departments.

The second is to adapt the educational process to market requirements, ensure its integration with production, and create an environment for the student to work on himself.

The third is to increase the scientific potential of higher education institutions, to develop science and innovation.

The fourth is to reduce red tape for faculty and students, and drastically reduce bureaucracy and corruption by digitizing the industry.

In order to effectively fulfill these tasks, it was emphasized that higher education institutions should be empowered to make independent decisions on academic and organizational management. Special attention was paid to the issue of the scientific potential of higher education institutions. For example, it was criticized that the scientific potential of 24 higher educational institutions is not even 25%, and 19 of them do not have a single professor or doctor of science. Therefore, the President gave instructions to double the number of quotas for doctoral studies next year, and to increase it by 50% every year from the following years. In fact, the work we have done cannot be said to be at the level of today's demand. After all, the priority tasks set by our head of state are not only the development of education, but also can be recognized as a modern program for the development of science-education-production relations, which will start a new stage of development. The implementation of this program in the future will serve to create specific mechanisms for the commercialization of the results of scientific research and innovative activities in each higher education and scientific research institution, and to increase the efficiency of applying scientific research to production.

The latest advances in science and technology, along with production, have made it possible to bring significant changes, innovations and modern teaching tools to the field of education. The introduction of these achievements into the field of education made it necessary to make significant changes to its traditional tasks. In this context, the problem of creating the necessary pedagogical conditions and creative environment for understanding and realizing the essence of educational reforms has arisen.

At the current modern stage of teacher training, State educational standards are the most important educational and regulatory document for scientific and methodological research. The analysis of educational standards shows that in the conditions of the educational cluster, it is impossible to achieve effective results in education without forming the competence of self-development in future pedagogues at the level of modern requirements. For this reason, attention has recently been paid to assessing the level of competencies of students and graduates of higher education institutions.

Pedagogical conditions are external conditions affecting the course of the pedagogical process, consciously designed by the pedagogue to one degree or another in order to achieve a specific result. It is clear from this that it is necessary to pre-design pedagogical conditions that are important for the development of an individual's psyche, skills and abilities, especially for the

formation of self-development competence in students in the conditions of an educational cluster. According to N. Ippalitova, N. Sterkhonova, pedagogical conditions are one of the components of the pedagogical system, and the possibilities of the educational and material-social environment, which affect the personal and procedural aspects of the same system, ensure its effective operation and development. reflects the present. According to their recognition, pedagogical conditions are conditions that ensure achievement of achievements in the educational process or, on the contrary, prevent it. We consider the most optimal pedagogical conditions for the formation of practical self-development competencies in future pedagogues based on a modern approach: individual-oriented, implemented at the expense of providing emotional comfort and social protection for students in the design of individual production education organization of education; increasing the student's educational motivation due to the formation of a positive attitude towards the chosen pedagogic profession; ensuring the practical orientation of all educational work that allows the teacher to design the educational and professional activities of students; joint solution of issues related to the formation of self-development compensations and strengthening of social cooperation, which implies mutually beneficial cooperation with educational institutions in cluster conditions, and provision of resource and methodical provision of pedagogical design priorities such as creating a focused special educational environment were defined.

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